

2-*p*-AMINOPHENYLMINO-4-THIAZOLIDONE AND SOME OF ITS DERIVATIVES

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2-*p*-Aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone and its arylidene derivatives have been prepared by reduction with iron and acetic acid of the corresponding 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone and its arylidene compounds. The compounds thus prepared have been mercurated and also brominated. The position of acetoxymercuri group, introduced on mercuration, has been determined. 2-*p*-Aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone does not undergo nuclear substitution on bromination. The fungicidal properties of both the brominated and mercurated compounds have been evaluated.

In course of our investigations, we have developed a new and very convenient route to the synthesis of thiazolidone compounds (Rout and Mahapatra, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2427). The method devised by us (illustrated here by the preparation of 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone) consists of heating aryl thiocarbamides with chloroacetic acid in absolute alcohol in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate, and has certain advantages over that of Desai, Hunter and Kopper (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1935, **54**, 118) in that the procedure adopted by us is more rapid and does not involve the isolation of the intermediate substituted formamidine-thiol-acetic acid. It has also been shown that some of these thiazolidone compounds can be successfully used in analytical procedures for estimation of Ag, Hg and Cu (Das and Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 16). In course of preparing different series of new thiazolidone derivatives and exploring new possibilities for their applications, it appeared of interest to prepare 2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, since the amino group would provide easy routes to the introduction of several therapeutically active groups like arsenic, sulphonamide, thiourea, thiosemicarbazide, etc. This compound could not obviously be prepared by the reaction of *p*-aminophenylthiourea with chloroacetic acid because of the presence of the reactive -NH₂ group which would condense with ease with chloroacetic acid. The only convenient route which suggested itself was by reduction of the corresponding 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone which could be easily obtained by reaction of 2-*p*-nitrophenylthiourea with chloroacetic acid. The reduction was effected by iron filings and glacial acetic acid in alcohol medium.

To prepare the corresponding arylidene derivative, the conventional method could not be applied. The potential carbonyl group would not only combine with the -CH₂ group of the thiazolidone nucleus but also with the NH₂ group of the substituted arylimino group. The method which was adopted here involved the reduction of the corresponding arylidene derivatives of 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, by iron filings and acetic acid, exactly in the same manner as in case of the parent compound, 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone.

The preparations of 2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone and its arylidene derivatives are illustrated in the Experimental. The preparations of the intermediate

products, 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone and its arylidene derivatives, are also described along with them.

The compound, 2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (in form of its acetyl derivative) has also been brominated. In the bromination of diaryl- ψ -thiohydantoins, it has been reported that the keto enol system is not affected and polybromide-addition compounds of highly complex nature are formed (Farooq and Hunter, this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 545; Choudhury, Desai, Hunter and Solangi, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1933, 52, 853). The thiazolidone compounds, studied here, however, do not possess the second aryl nucleus which is substituted by bromine in case of diaryl- ψ -thiohydantoin. A study of the behaviour of this compound towards bromine, likely to prove of interest, was therefore undertaken. On treatment of the thiazolidone compound with bromine in chloroform under ice-cooling, a vermilion-coloured bromine-addition compound was formed. Attempts to determine the nature of this complex revealed that all the bromine was in a labile state as it was completely removed by sulphurous acid and also HgO, regenerating the original compound. These observations completely rule out the following possibilities: (i) addition of bromine to the double bond of 2-phenylimino grouping in the original thiazolidone, (ii) the formation of a sulphonium bromine in which case, on treatment with HgO, a sulphoxide and not the original thiazolidone would have been formed; (iii) nuclear substitution of the aryl nucleus. Hence, the bromine-addition compound cannot be of the nature of hydroperbromide and may be dibromide of the type formed between benzthiazole and bromine in an inert solvent (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 125; Dyson, *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 147).

Since brominated thiazolidone (with bromine attached to the ring) could not be obtained in this manner, bromination of arylidene derivatives of thiazolidones was undertaken. Bromine reacted with the vinyl group, yielding stable dibromides and one of the two bromine atoms was attached to the thiazolidone ring. Only four such compounds have been brominated. The fungicidal activities of these compounds have also been determined.

2-*p*-Aminophenyliminothiazolidone and three of its arylidene derivatives have also been mercurated. The acetoxymercuri group enters the arylimino group. Other possibilities have been ruled out. The compound is not decomposed by alkali, thus indicating that Hg does not replace the H-atom of the -NH group in position-3. The acetoxymercuri group does not substitute the -CH₂ group as both the thiazolidone and its arylidene products can be mercurated under identical conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-*p*-Aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone was prepared by reduction of 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, which in turn was prepared as follows:

A mixture of *p*-nitrophenylthiourea (6 g.), monochloroacetic acid (3 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) and absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and then poured into cold water. The

yellow precipitate formed was allowed to settle and filtered. It was washed several times with hot water, recrystallised from alcohol and dried, m.p. 225°, yield 70%. (Found: S, 13.72. $C_8H_7O_2N_2S$ requires S, 13.5 per cent).

A mixture of 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (5 g.), alcohol (36 c.c.), iron filings (20 g.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.) was refluxed with stirring for one hour. Glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) was again added to the mixture and stirring was continued for two hours more. The mixture was basified with sodium carbonate and filtered while hot. Alcohol was removed by distillation. The aqueous mixture was further evaporated till the bulk was considerably reduced. It was cooled and on addition of water 2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone separated out. It was filtered and the residue was washed well with cold water and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 206°, yield 50%. (Found: S, 15.29. $C_8H_9ON_2S$ requires S, 15.46 per cent).

5-Benzylidene-2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone was prepared by reduction of 5-benzylidene-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, which in turn was prepared as follows:

A mixture of benzaldehyde (1 g.) and 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (1.5 g.) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (about 25 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (about 1.5 g.) on an asbestos wiregauze for 2 hours. The clear solution after being cooled was poured into water yielding a dirty yellow precipitate. After stirring thoroughly and allowing the precipitate to stand overnight, the solution was filtered off, the precipitate washed well in water and it was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 311°, yield 75%. (Found: S, 10.13. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 9.85 per cent).

5-Benzylidene-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone was reduced by iron filings and glacial acetic acid in presence of alcohol in the manner already described, m.p. above 320°, yield 75%. (Found: S, 11.10. $C_{16}H_{13}ON_2S$ requires S, 10.84 per cent).

TABLE I.

5-Arylidene-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidones.

Comp. No.	Aldehydes providing the arylidene group.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	Benzaldehyde	311°	75%	10.13	9.80
2	<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	252°	80	10.89	10.47
3	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	>300°	70	10.03	9.37
4	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	264°	50	8.84	8.65
5	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	247°	70	9.25	8.65
6	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	301°	70	9.16	8.65
7	Anisaldehyde	302°	74	9.45	9.90
8	Cinnamaldehyde	265°	75	9.62	9.10
9	Vanillin	256°	80	10.20	9.80

TABLE II

5-Arylidene-2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidones.

Comp. No.	Aldehydes providing the arylidene group.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur	
				Found.	Calc.
10	Benzaldehyde	>340°	75%	11.29	10.84
11	<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	180°	65	10.40	10.28
12	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	>300°	60	10.35	10.28
13	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	290° (d)	60	9.81	9.40
14	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	>300°	65	9.56	9.60
15	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	Do	70	9.91	9.40
16	Anisaldehyde	280° (d)	50	10.10	9.84
17	Cinnamaldehyde	167°	60	9.50	9.90
18	Vanillin	255°	70	9.81	9.80

Bromination of 2-p-Acetamidophenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—A solution of 2-*p*-acetamidophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (1 g.) in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 2 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was kept in ice for 1 hour. As no crystallisation took place, the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when a vermilion-coloured bromine-addition compound separated. It was collected on a glass-sintered crucible and dried in vacuum over potassium hydroxide, paraffin wax and anhydrous calcium chloride. An orange product was obtained, m.p. 195°.

All the bromine in this compound was in a labile state. The percentage of labile bromine, before treatment with sulphurous acid, was estimated by dissolving the bromine-addition compound in chloroform to which a drop or two of acetic acid had been added and then adding a strong solution of potassium iodide. The iodine liberated on shaking the mixture was titrated with *N*/20 sodium thiosulphate solution. Analysis indicated the presence of two bromine atoms. (Found: Labile Br, 38.48. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_3Br_2S$, requires Br, 39.1 per cent).

5-Bromo-5-phenylbromomethyl-2-p-acetamidophenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—A solution of 5-benzylidene-2-*p*-acetamidophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (1 g.) in chloroform (40 c.c.) was cooled to about 0° and then treated with bromine (2 c.c.) in chloroform (8 to 10 c.c.) and the mixture was kept in ice for 1 hour. On concentrating the solution under reduced pressure, a deep red product was obtained which on treatment with sulphurous acid and subsequent basification with ammonia furnished the dibromide of the starting material, m.p. 205°, yield 80%. (Found: Br, 31.96; S, 6.25. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_3Br_2S$ requires Br, 32.19; S, 6.44 per cent).

TABLE III

5-Bromo-5-arylbromomethyl-2-(*p*-acetamidophenylimino)-4-thiazolidone.

Aldehydes.	M.P.	% Bromine.		% Sulphur.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	225°	29.35	29.52	5.70	5.0
Anisaldehyde	230°	30.12	30.36	5.92	6.07
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	190°	29.55	29.63	5.68	5.93

2-(o-Acetoxymercuri-p-aminophenylimino)-4-thiazolidone.—A solution of mercuric acetate (2 g.) in 30 to 40 c.c. of water, acidified with 3 to 4 drops of glacial acetic acid, was treated with an alcohol-dilute acetic acid solution of 2-*p*-aminophenylimino-4-thiazolidone (1 g.), and the mixture was stirred vigorously for 20 to 15 minutes, when a precipitate appeared. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight with occasional stirring and then filtered. The precipitate was washed with hot water 3 to 4 times and then with very dilute acetic acid. Finally it was washed with alcohol, m.p. 207°, yield 75%. (Found: S, 6.56; Hg, 42.85. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_2SH_2$ requires S, 6.88; Hg, 43.01 per cent).

5-Benzylidene-2-(o-acetoxymercuri-p-aminophenylimino)-4-thiazolidone.—An alcohol-dilute acetic acid solution of 5-benzylidene-2-(*o*-acetoxymercuri-*p*-aminophenylimino)-4-thiazolidone (1.3 g.) was mixed with vigorous stirring with an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (3 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about half an hour and then vigorously stirred again for 20 minutes and kept overnight and then filtered. It was purified as the preceding compound, m.p. 205°, yield 75%. (Found: Hg, 35.95. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_2SHg$ requires Hg, 36.2 per cent).

TABLE IV

5-Arylidene-2-(o-acetoxymercuri-p-aminophenylimino)-4-thiazolidone.

Aldehydes.	M.P.	Yield.	% Mercury.	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	205°	75%	33.12	33.44
Cinnamaldehyde	230°	80	34.21	34.54
Anisaldehyde	235°	75	34.41	34.30

Fungicidal activity was assayed with the test fungus as reported by Rout and Pujari (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 13). The mercurated compounds were very effective, completely inhibiting spore germination even at a dilution of 5 to 6 p.p.m. The dibromide compounds were active nearly to the same extent.

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